

IPT Conference Proceedings

X École Polytechnique, Paris, France, 2023

International Physicists' Tournament

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IPT Conference Proceedings

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by

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Preface by our president

Dear IPT Community,

In the IPT, we are committed to enriching your educational experience.

You may not know yet what career path you will be choosing. It may be setting up your own business, making striking innovations or exploring the beauty of physics. It is very much up to you to choose. In the modern world, developing a diverse skill toolbox is a winning strategy. We are proud to give you a platform where you can train those skills - learn how to debate, present, pitch, solder and run numerical simulations.

The IPT gives you many opportunities to shine and explore. Today, we are proud to present the success of one of the most recent projects - the IPT Conference Proceeding. The IPT Conference concept has evolved through the year from a free presentations format, where the participants can chat about not-played problems, to an outstanding event within the IPT week. Now, the IPT Conference floor is open for everyone - non-finalists, national selection participants and just physics enthusiasts.

The IPT Conference is a format, more conventional to the academic environment - if pursuing this path, you may find yourself writing abstracts and proceedings quite often. However, even outside the research career, you will find it helpful to concisely summarise months of your research and highlight the most exciting outcomes.

We thank our contributors, who submitted their proceedings to this issue - you are already in history as the authors of the very first IPT Conference Proceeding. We encourage everyone to take part in the next issues - do not hesitate to present at the IPT Conference and submit your abstracts.

Anastasiia Vasylchenkova
President of the IPT
March 2024

A word to the students

Dear IPT participants,

It is with great joy that we bring to life the 1st IPT Conference Proceedings! After many years with thrilling problems, amazing experiments, and brilliant solutions, it was finally time to give some space for solutions of the entire community as well, not just the ones we see at the tournament. In these proceedings, you will find abstracts and extended abstracts of students that participated in the IPT Conference at the X École Polytechnique, Paris, France, which became the second edition in which students from the whole world (not just the ones that were attending the competition on-site) could join us and share their solutions online.

As the tournament itself grows and embraces new countries, it is great to see that no effort towards the IPT goes unrewarded— therefore making the discussions accessible to all is very important and necessary. It is also an opportunity for all students to train their scientific communication abilities in a new way. Now, IPT students can participate in the entire circle of the scientific life: 1) conducting research experimentally and theoretically to solve the problems, 2) writing a scientific article to pass the preselection process, 3) formatting their solutions in a 10-minute presentation, 4) publish papers based on IPT problems, and now 5) write abstracts and/or extended abstracts just like in other scientific conferences.

I appreciate the effort of the students who took time to write their abstracts for these proceedings. We are all excited to see this new arm of the IPT grow even more each year as well!

Matheus Azevedo Silva Pessôa
Editor of the IPT Conference Proceedings and
Member of the Executive Committee of the IPT
March 2024

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The IPT Problems

During the competition, we saw solutions of all 17 IPT problems. In these proceedings, present abstracts from 6 of these problems, which are listed below.

Match Counting

How accurately can you determine the number of matches in a matchbox from the sound it makes when you shake it? Can the same methods be applied to a box containing chewing gums?

Pringles Stack Ring

It is possible to build structures by stacking Pringles on top of one another in various configurations. What are the physical parameters that allow some geometric patterns to be constructed? What is the largest stack ring that can be built? What maximal weight can it support?

The Chalk Trick

It is possible to draw continuous lines in a blackboard with chalk. However, by changing the angle of contact, the line drawn on the board becomes a dotted line, though the movement is still continuous. What parameters from the relative movement between the chalk and the board can be inferred from the resulting trace? Is it possible to infer anything about the dimensions of the chalk?

Dancing Lights

Put a membrane with a mirror over a speaker. Then project the reflection of a laser pointer over a screen. By driving the speaker with single or multiple frequencies you may observe lines and shapes projected in the screen. Given a closed trajectory in 2D of a single line, find the input on the speaker required to "paint" the line. Can you also "rotate" the line as you desire? Investigate the limitations.

Glass Halo

Glittering circles can be seen when light from a source with small angular size passes through a glass. On closer examination they appear to be composed of small scratches and structural inhomogeneities. In some cases, specific rays can be seen, diverging from the light source (left part of the photo). Under which conditions such circle halos and lines can be seen? Investigate their geometrical properties and what shapes you can engineer.

Bubble love and tensions

When two soap bubbles collide, they may rebound or coalesce. Find the conditions for both phenomena to occur.

1

Analysis of optical pattern formation on glass

Maressa Pimenta Sampaio, Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil

In optics, reflection and refraction are established subjects. However, for light passing through a glass, the formation of particular patterns has not been extensively explored [1]. Here we investigate two of them: glittering circles and diverging rays. Experimentally, we use various glass plates, registering each reflected outcome. Thus, we determine the conditions to form each pattern, namely, (a) randomly scratched plates produce the halos, and (b) bright spots tend to generate diverging rays, which are an optical distortion. Also, we study the density of halos and engineer new shapes using specular holography [2]. A simulation allows us to confirm the optical regime and provides comparative results to our experimental data. In it, we assume, among other details, that (1) the reflected and transmitted patterns are equal and (2) that we are working with geometric optics. The first assumption is valid in the literature for circumstances satisfied in our experiments. The second premise arose after examining the geometric properties of the glass with the Defocusing Microscopy technique [3]. Our numerical results agree well with the experimental ones, leading us to conclude that the proposed model gives an initial explanation for the phenomenon of halo formation.

Figure 1.1: Top: polished plate, horizontally scratched plate, and vertically scratched plate. Bottom: randomly scratched plate with 80 grit sandpaper, 150 grit sandpaper, and 280 grit sandpaper.

2

Counting matches from their sound

Giovanna Fernandes do Valle, Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil

A methodology was developed to determine the number of objects inside a box based on the sound it makes when it is shaken. Experiments were conducted using matches inside a matchbox, and later with a box containing chewing gums. The apparatus used was a damped oscillator, made with simple materials: a ruler attached to a fixed surface at one of its ends, the matchbox attached to the free end of the ruler, and a microphone. The audio analysis was made with software Audacity.

The experiment consisted in putting the system to oscillate, by moving down the free end of the ruler. The audio was recorded from the moment the ruler was released and started oscillating, until it stopped. The process was carried out for different amounts of matches, from the minimum (0) to the maximum capacity of the box (55), varying 5 by 5. Data analyzed was of the sound amplitude as a function of time for each amount of objects. By summing the squares of the amplitudes, a quantity A was obtained, which is proportional to the system energy and whose plot as a function of the number of matches N produced an asymmetrical curve peaked at N_{peak} . Based on it, there were two possible values for an unknown N corresponding to a new recorded sound. It was then noted that the duration DT of the movement presented a minimum as a function of N , located at $N_{min} > N_{peak}$. By comparing both $A \times N$ and $\Delta t \times N$ curves, it was possible to determine the amount of matches in the box with an uncertainty equal to 3.

The same method was successfully tested for a candy box, leading to the conclusion that it is also applicable to other objects.

3

The formation and endurance of stacked Pringle structures

Iason Kazazis, University of Athens, Greece

Structures by stacked Pringles on top of one another, in various configurations can be formed, the most distinct of them being the Pringle stack ring, which exhibits several interesting structural properties. In this paper, the physical parameters that allow the construction of different patterns are investigated, while also focusing on the features of the stack ring structure such as its size and structural integrity. Furthermore, the ability of this structure to support external weight, is examined both theoretically and experimentally. To study the structures, an original, problem-specific notation has been developed based on "the stacking problem" for rhomboid stacks [4]. Two different variable-weight experimental setups were constructed to perform press tests for a variety of load distributions. Experimental and theoretical results as well as future study processes and ideas are discussed. Pringles are saddle shaped chips, made to be stackable. For that purpose, each one is almost identical to another. Pringles are observed to be stiff, the material parameters are assumed to have very low elastic modulus, fracture strain and plastic displacement. The Pringle-Pringle friction coefficient is similar to Al-Al but the material is less dense. These factors make Pringle chips the ideal material for these structures. Practically most rings structures, that are crafted, are formulaically indescribable. Consequently, it is important for a formation to be able to be formally described. The structures are expected to have specific properties to balance with no external interferences. A simple yet effective setup was devised to measure the weight support a ring can have before collapse. The press consisted of thin wood sheet which could be lowered or raised and support weight without bending significantly. A scale, water or rice for precise weight measurements were utilised. The top plank could move steadily using either two columns or drawer slides.

4

Refraction and reflection on dirty and scratched surfaces

Lucas Nogueira Roberto, State University of Campinas, Brazil

When we observe a scratched piece of material, usually a glass or metal, it's possible to observe shiny segments that compose glittering circles, in some cases when the camera lens is smudge or dirty some flare is also visible. Our study is a proposal of experimental study about these imaging phenomenon, explaining its physics using basic principles and investigating shapes possible to be draw using a arbitrary patterns of scratches.

5

An Experimental Investigation of "The Chalk Trick"

Viktor Sundström, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden

This study investigates the resulting trace when drawing dotted lines on a blackboard using a chalk. It is based on the problem "The Chalk Trick" from the 2023 edition of the International Physics Tournament (IPT). A one dimensional model for the distance between dots was constructed, modeling the chalk movement as a spring with a varying frictional force. The model could be fitted to experimental data, but cannot be used to uniquely characterize how the a line was drawn based on the resulting pattern alone. A mechanical device that was able to draw dotted lines using the same mechanisms was also constructed. Using this device the following was observed : a linear trend between movement velocity and distance was found (Pearson Coefficient 0.99), a monotone trend between stiffness of springs used in the device and distance between dots, and no clear trend between applied force and distance between dots. By analyzing recordings of the drawing process of 16 lines the study verified the velocity trend (Pearson coefficient 0.84). The collected data also suggests that the angle that the chalk hits the board limits the achievable drawing velocity.

Figure 5.1: a) Skipping lines being traced by a chalk on the board by hand motion. b) Experimental setup to reproduce the skipping lines.

6

Rebound condition of colliding soap bubbles depending on velocity

Ihor Sachok, Kyiv National University, Ukraine

In my work effects that can occur when soap bubbles collide are divided into two: rebound and coalescence. In practice there are two possible cases of coalescence: merging and formation of a double, but we consider it as one. In our work we propose an experimental set up that allows to make soap bubbles of the same mass every time and vary radiuses and velocities. We research dependence of velocity on condition of rebound. For this we propose simple theory that consider forces that act on a soap bubble that falls: force of Laplace pressure, gravity force and Van der Waals force and write down motion equation. From additional experiment we get parameters of the system. Finally, using numerical methods, we fit parameter of the system, that we cannot find, according to our experiment. From it we get critical velocity and divide coordinate space into two phases: coalescence and rebound. As a result, we get 3d graph of dividing surface in coordinates: first radius, second radius and velocity [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10].

Figure 6.1: a) Experimental setup. b) Example of experimental measurements using the Tracker software.

7

Dancing Lights

Renan Gomes Alvim, Pietra Dominicini Zanni, Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil

The set up for the IPT problem “Dancing lights” consists of a membrane attached to a recipient with a speaker inside. By sticking a mirror on the membrane and pointing a laser on it, when the speaker is driven with a single or multiple frequencies, the reflected laser pointer “paints” figures on a screen. These are Lissajous figures. The picture has its XY coordinates (on the screen it is being projected) controlled by the movement of the membrane, which in turn is controlled by the sound coming from the speaker. Therefore, to determine how a figure arises from a specific sound frequency emitted by the speaker it is necessary to understand how the membrane moves.

The membrane was modeled as a two-dimensional surface with uniform stiffness and attached to a circular or a square boundary. The normal modes of vibration were determined experimentally using salt to create Chladni patterns and used as a reliable way to control the figure formation. By comparing the experimental figures with those of the model, limitations such as the interaction between the membrane and its boundary, the air and the sound intensity of the speaker were identified.

After obtaining a relatively reliable way of connecting a figure with one single frequency input from the speaker, the next step was to determine the figures that arise when two or more frequencies were applied. It was found that the new figures were a sum in the XY coordinates of the functions associated with each frequency. Furthermore, the figure rotation that can happen sometimes was identified as a special case of applying multiple frequencies, where the new figure is too big to be painted as a whole before the human eye can process it.

The Chalk Trick, extended abstract

Anne Sofie Darket, Technical University of Denmark, Denmark

We divided the problem into two main parts:

- Forward problem: Given parameters for the relative movement between chalk and blackboard + dimensions of the chalk, what is the resulting pattern?
- Inverse problem: Given the pattern, what were the relative movement between chalk and blackboard + dimensions of the chalk?

Forward problem

We set up a theoretical model for the chalk movement while it was touching the blackboard (BB), and while it was in the air respectively.

Using classical mechanics for a rigid body (see Figure 1 for force diagram), we found an upper and lower bound on the critical angle between the chalk and blackboard right before the chalk lost contact with the board,

$$\theta_{min} \approx \cot(\mu_s) - \beta, \theta_{max} = \frac{\pi}{2} - \beta$$

where β is a geometrical parameter of the chalk, and μ_s is the static coefficient of friction. This was verified in a series of experiments by hand (see Figure 2 for experimental setup).

Tracking the motion, we found the chalk to be oscillating while in the air (see Figure 3), allowing us to model the grip on the chalk as a spring. With this, we set up a model for predicting the distance between dots, which was verified in a similar series of experiments.

Inverse problem

Due to the large number of variables in the chalk movement (speed, angle of contact, chalk length, tightness of grip, etc.), we are not able to infer anything from the dotted pattern alone as there are not enough variables to be measured from the pattern (dot distance, shape, etc.) to cover all the input parameters. In conclusion, we were able to solve the forward problem, but not the inverse.

Figure 8.1: a) Force diagram of the chalk touching the blackboard. Point p is where the chalk is held, and F, f are the components of the forces from the hand. b) Experimental setup. The length of the chalk was used as reference, and the motion of point p and q was tracked using Tracker. c) The angle between chalk and board vs time. The chalk is seen to oscillate during the time in the air.

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